

MEASURING THE EMPLOYEE INTERACTIONS TOWARDS CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN LANGKAWI ISLAND HOPPING SERVICES

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research is to measure the employee interactions towards customer satisfaction in specific areas related to island hopping in one of the popular tourist destinations in Malaysia. Island hopping is one of the most popular activities enjoyed by the tourist involving both local and international visitors. The need to understand the customer expectations is vital due to high competition and with the intention to move forward in providing excellent services. 200 valid questionnaires was collected via a purposive sampling method and analyzed using Smart-PLS software 3.0. This study used a quantitative approach where the use of questionnaires is the best in providing the customers with feedback. There are overall 15 items used in the questionnaires. All items were adapted from past research. The survey used 7 points Likert scales for a more accurate response from respondents. Customers may opt to choose the reaction from 1= strongly disagree, and 7=strongly agree. Five hundred questionnaires form were distributed among the customers who experienced the island hopping services while their visit to Langkawi. Results indicates that emotions and perceived control is positively related to customer satisfaction while roles perception and customer categories are negatively related to customer satisfaction. The findings is important to all the industry players in order to strengthen their market positioning and sustain in the market.

KEYWORDS: Roles perception, customer categories, emotions, perceived control

I. INTRODUCTION

A recent tourism report indicates that there are 2.7 million visitors to Langkawi in 2019. The numbers show a 4.2 increase compared to the total visitors in 2018[1]. It was also mentioned that most of the visitors are local. Langkawi is a popular tourist destination because of its duty-free status, which has been established since 1987. Overall there are more than 4 million visitors to Langkawi, and the target is to achieve more than 5 million visitors by the year 2020. Besides shopping, customers visited Langkawi for the island hopping activities[2]. There are more than 100 small tour operators registered with the state council.

High numbers of players in the industry lead to fierce competition among them. The service provider must compete to sustain in the business[3]. Some may collaborate with their strategic partners, such as travel agents from the outside state, for long-term business sustainability. The service provider needs to portray their advantage in order to attract more customers. Past research indicates that one way to get more customers and sustain in business is by providing excellent service that can surpass customer expectations [4]. Such services will contribute to customer satisfaction. Scholars in Marketing [5] claimed that the effort to provide high-quality services to customers that lead to customer satisfaction would be lavish. There are so many benefits that customers may play in business sustainability, especially for a small business operator for the island hopping services.

Most of the advertisements to Langkawi is promoting the island hopping tour. Only registered small business operator is allowed to run the business. The destination, route, and activities are the same among all the operators [1]. There are also not many options for the selection of boats. Based on that, the competition among the operators is solely based on the services offered. The service provider needs to pay attention to customer expectations so that they can prepare themselves to be better than others [6].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a state of customer feeling based on their experiences of products or services[5]. It is a measure of the overall products or services received by the customer. Ideally, the customer will be satisfied if the total experiences meet or more than customer expectations[7]. Anything below customer expectations will result in unhappy and dissatisfied. Past research [8], [9] stated that it is vital for the service-based organization to monitor customer satisfaction. Monitoring customer happiness is complex [10], [11], and after all, it involves

many other elements that lead towards customer satisfaction. It is also highlighted [8], [9] that customer satisfaction is not as simple as measuring business profit or revenue. Therefore, the service provider must know the outcome of their services, whether it meets customer expectations [12].

Understanding customers is not comfortable, especially in the 21st century. Customer is complicated and highly demanding[13]. They have access to information and very knowledgeable. Social media, blogs, and websites lead to more access to products and services expectations. Customer can share their experiences, comment, and review of their past experiences. Those experiences shared in the online platform reach an unlimited market[14]. The customer today can even share their experiences online for others to observed virtually.

Customer satisfaction is essential to business organizations as they will remain in the customer lifecycle[14]. Past researchers highlighted that keeping customers is much cheaper than acquiring a new one. It was mentioned that converting customers is six times more expensive than keeping the current customer[15]. A satisfied customer is more tolerable to the service provider, especially when there is a need to increase the prices[16]. The service provider can easily explain the reason and justify it.

It was also highlighted that customer satisfaction can keep the brand image in the right positions. Satisfied customer, especially those customers that are fond in sharing their experiences will share their overall experiences that may spark other people interest to consume the products as well[14]. However, negative experiences will lead to customer word of mouth or even worse through internet-based communications that may reach large numbers of people. Negative experiences indirectly carry a negative brand image of the service providers as they failed to satisfied the customer.

Past researchers [17] also indicate that satisfied customers will keep returning to the service provider. The longer the service provider managed to keep the customer satisfied, the more frequent that the customer will come back to the service providers. It was also highlighted [18], [19] that customer retention is a partial step to achieving loyalty. The relationship between the service provider and customer satisfaction is essential as it will cultivate the loyalty status. A customer that enjoys the overall satisfying experiences overtimes will later have started to appreciate the relationship. A loyal customer will bring a lot of more significant benefits to the service provider over the long term. It was also highlighted by [17] that dissatisfied customer tends to share their negative experiences with their close friend and family. Recent research indicates that unsatisfied customers tend to tell 10 to twenty other customers covering both current and prospective[20]. The bad experiences than will spread and accumulated exponentially. Such a thing will lead to a high cost to the service providers in keeping their marketing and promotional campaigns.

Overall the benefits of keeping the customer satisfied are essential to the service provider as it brings a more significant impact on sustainability and market growth. It was said [21], [22] that customer satisfaction may reduce competitive switching behavior. Competition in business within the industry usually is fierce as they compete over the same size as the target market. Competitors will end up come out with creative advertising and add more value to the customer. Such a thing may impact the effort by inviting customers from others to switch to their products or services. Satisfied customers according to [23], [24] will not easily be influenced by such action by competitors and thus secure the market share of current service providers.

Customer satisfaction in the case of island hopping services in Langkawi is expected to share the same flow as of any other cycle of other service providers[25]. Island hopping operators may need to look at the ways in promoting customer satisfaction to induce the positive experiences to gain the benefits of customer satisfaction.

2.2 Customer Interactions

Customer interactions are the communication between the service provider and customers. The interaction process is the chance for the service provider to get closer to the customer to build a relationship. That interaction is supposed to be an excellent opportunity for the service provider to understand the customer needs and expectations so that the service delivery can be customized to meet customer expectations. Past research [6] suggested that service providers take the opportunity in interaction with customers to prepare themselves in service delivery. It was also highlighted [26] that not all types of service delivery can communicate with a customer before the service delivery. Island hopping services is one of a kind services that enable the opportunity for the service operator to get to know their customer and keeping them informed along the process of customer experiences[27]. Such a situation should be made a priority to maintain and increase the level of customer satisfaction.

The benefits of customer interactions are very much significant. The service provider must ensure that they have competent staff in delivering the services. Employees must have at least be empathy in communication with customers[28]. Employees must try to understand the customer state of mind primarily related to the first time

customer. There will be a situation where the customer could be afraid of a lack of confidence. Employee interactions may provide the customer to feel comfortable and confident in the case of island hopping activities[29].

Researcher [10], [30] recommended that service providers improve employee interactions as it can improve customer acquisition. Customer who is happy and satisfied especially from the employee interactions will share their experiences and tell others about their experiences. In Marketing, based on research [12], 90% of the customer was said to rely on recommendations before deciding on certain things. The recommendation could be from word of mouth or any other social media platform such as Instagram, Facebook, or twitter. A service provider that emphasizes employee interactions to instill trust may gain the benefits of better customer acquisition rather than need to make a tremendous effort to promote and capture potential customer attention[31].

Employee interactions also contribute to customer conversions [32]. An existing customer may that enjoyed their experience may stay in the customer life cycle for a longer time. Customer conversion is not solely on increasing revenue[14], but it is instead to build a stronger relationship between the service provider and the customer. Good experience in employee-customer may also convert the state of the customer mind from seeking options to the immediate decision[32]. The role of employee interactions cannot be a doubt as much past research indicates its importance. However, it very much depends on the nature of services and industry.

Past researcher indicates [33] that employee interactions could lead to the reduction of marketing budget. The fact is that interactions between the service provider and customer aim to get more knowledge and better understand customers. Frequent communications can enable the service provider to know exactly what the customer needs. To the extends, the service provider can have a multi segmentation based on the customer category. Good interactions can lead service providers to differentiate what is domestic and international are looking[16]. They will also understand the needs of customers based on different geographical areas and cultures. Knowing about customers will enable the service customer to prepare themselves for a good marketing strategy rather than in the guessing works.

Recent research [34] indicates that employee interactions can improve customers' trust in the service provider. The belief is essential, especially when there is anything that happened during the island hopping. It may have happened that during the island hopping, customers may face some challenges due to weather. In a typical situation, customers will quickly get panic, but employee interactions will play a role in gaining trust from customers. What is essential on the island hoping is the communication between employee and customer so that customer may not jump into conclusion that may lead to negative experiences. Such a thing has been reported by [35], where the employee interactions may help the service provider keep the brand image during the crisis. Crisis in the case of island hopping is more towards the overall boat trips that some time may not smooth as expected due to the seas and weather.

It has been reported repeatedly [36] that overall positive customer experiences may lead to customer satisfaction and finally being loyal. The global customer experiences are the foundation of customer satisfaction. Chances that the customer becomes satisfied with nothing to happen are very slim. There must be something that customers attracted or put a high value on the overall experiences[16]. In the case of island hoping, employee interactions are really important besides tangible things and matters such as the boat used for the trips.

Service providers in Langkawi especially need to be aware that employee interactions are one of the critical competencies that they can add internally[37]. There are many other factors but derived from the external and almost being standard in terms of process, procedures, and destination. Most of the service providers using the same type of boats, same process, and same destination. The only thing that the service provider can make a difference is through their communications. Excellent communication, as mentioned by [36], is one of the essential elements in getting the support, trust, and positive brand image. The service provider will gain market growth, and market share over the long term as the excellent services will spread, and many will look after the services by the identified service provider.

Past research [16] indicates that service providers should have trained their staff to understand customers and be part of the customer to understand them better; employees should be able to show empathy and gratitude to break the communication gap. There should not be a gap or standard treatment between one to another customer[37]. Besides that, it was also recommended that employees be more conscientious and responsible. Employees need to follow up on the customer situation from time to time and ask whether there is any support or help they may look after. Customers usually will become happy if the employee can react to their problem by the first interactions[38]. The challenges are when the service provider faces a group of customers where each customer may have different characteristics and expectations. Excellent communication based on customer

understanding and experience will help the service provider handle them at one go. Such things will create happiness and satisfaction among customers [39].

It is also vital for the employee to practice transparency in communication. The service provider needs to tell the potential customer the type of experience the customer will go through and the level of difficulty. The employee should brief customers on their overall trips and explained what they should expect. The pre-emphasis on the expectation may provide customers with some essential preparation that will reduce dissatisfaction or negative experiences. It was highlighted [40] that a reasonable employee will always ask customer feedback. That feedback is a high value to the service provider. They may improve their services in terms of the process to enhance customer experiences.

At any time, the service provider should have focused on delighting their customer [41]. Island hopping needs a lot of interactions since the employee will be together with the customer over a specific period when it is not known to the customer. Trust and confidence are essential to reduce the worrisome feeling and allow customers to use their time with full joy.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study seeks to investigate the relationship between customer interaction towards customer satisfaction in the island hopping services at Langkawi, Malaysia. Data collected addresses how employee interactions and communications can lead to customer satisfaction during the services period, which later can be translated as customer experiences. This study used a quantitative approach where the use of questionnaires is the best in providing the customers with feedback. There are overall 15 items used in the questionnaires. All items were adapted from past research. The survey used 7 points Likert scales for a more accurate response from respondents. Customers may opt to choose the reaction from 1= strongly disagree, and 7=strongly agree. Five hundred questionnaires form were distributed among the customers who experienced the island hopping services while their visit to Langkawi. Two main locations selected for the questionnaire distribution are the International airport and the main ferry jetty to the mainland. Three hundred five usable data managed to be collected over five days of data collection exercises.

IV. FINDINGS

Table 1 shows the summary statistics of the constructs used in the research. A value for emotions is 0.801, role perceptions (0.812), perceived control (0.823), customer categories (0.811) and customer satisfaction (0.852). All α readings were good and above the minimum recommended value. Emotions have the highest mean (5.983), while role perceptions are 4.789.

Table 1: Summary statistics of the questionnaire survey

Constructs	No. of items	Mean	SD	α
Emotions	5	5.250	0.125	0.801
Role perceptions	4	4.755	1.187	0.812
Perceived control	5	5.725	1.088	0.823
Customer categories	4	5.150	1.224	0.811
Customer satisfaction	4	5.300	1.311	0.852

Notes: SD, standard deviation, α , Cronbach's overall α 0.824

Table 2 depicts the result of the principal component analysis. The factors with values higher than 1 was considered for the study. All the 22 items were found with their communalities greater than 0.50 and were retained for the analysis.

Table 2: Result of principal component analysis

Items	Emotions	Role perceptions	Perceived control	Customer categories	Customer satisfaction
EO 1	0.814				
EO 2	0.702				
EO 3	0.832				
EO 4	0.813				
EO 5	0.704				
RP 1		0.722			

RP 2		0.802			
RP 3		0.833			
RP 4		0.724			
PC 1			0.814		
PC 2			0.806		
PC 3			0.670		
PC 4			0.825		
PC 5			0.819		
CC 1				0.870	
CC 2				0.866	
CC 3				0.847	
CC 4				0.799	
CS 1					0.911
CS 2					0.920
CS 3					0.815
CS 4					0.825
Eigenvalue	8.536	4.227	2.663	2.413	1.799
Variance explained (%)	35.530	17.055	11.361	11.305	5.895

Table 3 represents the measurement model results in which the result for composite reliability (CR) for all constructs is 0.88, 0.95, 0.96, 0.91, and 0.93. All composite reliabilities were also larger than the commonly accepted cutoff value of 0.60. AVE represents average variance extracted for the constructs is reported as 0.68, 0.74, 0.79, 0.90 and 0.92.

Table 3: Measurement model results constructs

Constructs variables	Standardized loadings	t-statistics	CR	AVE
Emotions				
EO 1	0.871	15.683**	0.88	0.68
EO 2	0.901	16.051**		
EO 3	0.702	12.236**		
EO 4	0.699	11.315**		
EO 5	0.678	11.718**		
Role perceptions				
RP 1	0.811	12.305**	0.95	0.74
RP 2	0.882	13.223**		
RP 3	0.925	14.611**		
RP 4	0.836	13.425**		
Perceived control				
PC 1	0.925	18.236**	0.96	0.79
PC 2	0.915	11.416**		
PC 3	0.720	19.233**		
PC 4	0.823	10.324**		
PC 5	0.824	10.211**		
Customer categories				
CC 1	0.902	17.306**	0.91	0.90
CC 2	0.936	18.514**		
CC 3	0.814	18.926**		
CC 4	0.825	11.322**		
Customer satisfaction				
CS 1	0.914	18.147**	0.93	0.92
CS 2	0.902	11.887**		
CS 3	0.836	19.536**		
CS 4	0.847	10.807**		

Table 4 represents the structural equation modeling results in which two relationships were found significant (emotions towards and perceived controls towards customer satisfaction). Another two were found not significant (role perceptions and customer categories towards customer satisfaction)

Table 4: Structural equation modeling results

Hypothesis	Std β	SE	Sig	Outcome
H1 :Emotions --> Customer satisfaction	0.169	0.039	**	H1: Supported
H2: Role perceptions --> Customer satisfaction	-0.029	0.032	P>0.05	H2: Not supported
H3: Perceived control --> Customer satisfaction	0.699	0.029	**	H3: Supported
H4: Customer categories --> Customer satisfaction	-0.065	0.023	P>0.05	H4: Not supported
Note: **P<0.01				

Four path coefficients were estimated to test the hypothesized, causal relationships in the model. The role perceptions and customer categories factors on customer' satisfaction at island hoping were low (β Role perceptions = -0.029 and β Customer categories = -0.065) and non-significant. Therefore, H2and H4 were not supported.

Conversely, emotions and perceived control factors have positive effects on customer' satisfaction (β Emotions = 0.169, β Perceived controls = 0.699), supporting H1 and H3. The proposed structural model and results of hypothesis testing are shown in Table 4 and Figure 1.

Figure 1: Confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation model. Path coefficients are standardized regression coefficient.

Notes: Solid lines represent statistically significant relationships, and broken lines represent non-significant relationships

V. DISCUSSIONS

The results indicate that at least two dimensions are positively significant towards customer satisfaction. Those are emotions and perceived controls. Service providers need to ensure that they manage the two areas carefully, which play important roles in customer satisfaction. Emotions in the context of island hoping are crucial, especially if the customers are first-time users and lack of confidence. Interactions are necessary and required to reduce the stress and doubtful of customers by explaining the process and procedures. Useful information about the safety guidelines and the overall expectations through the journey will provide customers some confidence.

Customer confidence is important as they need to enjoy the trips from the beginning rather than towards the end. Good interactions will manage to solve customer worry and instill trust and confidence.

Perceived controls, at the same time closely related to the customer confidence and positive state of mind towards the journey. A customer that never goes through the island hopping experiences will always worry mind, and afraid something terrible happens during their trip. Interactions may solve the problems through proper communications. Besides verbal, service providers can also provide information through video and testimonial from customers. Good interactions will keep the customer happy and increase their perceived control towards the activities.

Customer categories play a less important role as service providers will treat everyone the same to ensure safety. The difference that can be seen is how the customer-managed their emotions before, during, and after the activities. The results could be different if the customers have been frequently exposed to the same activities and destinations. Otherwise, it will be the same and equal to the rest. The same goes for the role perceptions which not significantly influence customer satisfaction because they will rely much on the service providers and follow the rules and safety guidelines prepared by the service provider and control by the authorities related to the sea sport and tourism. Service providers need to be more prepared to manage future customers and focus on the important role that can lead to customer satisfaction.

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